

THE EFFECTS OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

Khamidov Doniyor Sadikovich

Ministry of Internal Affairs
of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Leader teacher of Fergana Academic Lyceum

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5918805>

Annotation: This article analyzes teaching methods as literary and stylistic device in Modern English language and its morphological characteristics.

Keywords: qualitative research, attractive structure, educational research, social constructivism, teaching analysis, games theory, qualitative methodologies

Аннотация: В статье анализируются приемы обучения как литературно-стилистический прием современного английского языка и его морфологические характеристики.

Ключевые слова: качественное исследование, привлекательная структура, педагогическое исследование, социальный конструктивизм, педагогический анализ, теория игр, качественные методологии.

Introduction. English, a global language, has become one of the dominant mediums in politics, economy, and education internationally. English nowadays is the major medium to communicate with the whole world and the main language used for international trade and academic study. Accordingly, possessing basic English proficiency has become one of the essential requirements for many students. Also, in society there is an obviously positive correlation that the better a person's English ability, the greater that person's chances for higher education, professional employment and promotion prospects. The significance of English, therefore, cannot be ignored. Interest in using language games as teaching and learning activities in educational contexts is on the rise. The aim of this paper is to examine the use of communicative language games for teaching and learning English at academic lyceums. The instrument used in this study was a survey questionnaire about participants' perspectives on the use of communicative language games in English lessons. The results of the study provided encouraging evidence to indicate that foreign language teachers generally appreciated the benefits and value of communicative game activities in the teaching of English language. The findings also suggested that when facing students with different

backgrounds, learning styles, needs, and expectations, teachers should be aware to take learners' individual variations into account and be more flexible in their use of communicative games in order to maximize educational effect. It is hoped that communicative language games will attract more attention and will be applied more widely in the classroom with more positive attitudes on the part of language teachers.

The typical English teaching methods are form-based and text-based, and many teachers adopt Grammar Translation Method or Audiolingual Method on their teaching. English is taught by using dialogues for repetition and memorization, along with lots of systematic and intensive drills on sentence patterns and grammar rules. Grammar is regarded as the cornerstone in English instruction, whereas conversational English is hardly practiced. There is no real communication in English classes. Acquiring linguistic knowledge becomes the end instead of any ability to appropriately use the language of English. It is, therefore, often discovered that through such methods some students have fundamental understanding of formulaic phrases, but are unable or too shy to put them to use, not to mention the difficulties in conversing with a fluent speaker. For those students, English language is not a practical language in which they can freely communicate with others, but merely another subject for examinations.

The most frequently used games in teaching English.

Discussion. The present study investigated the effects of teaching English through games. The findings of world experience are revealing that students are significantly improving in vocabulary knowledge and ability to communicate. Moreover, they are tending to have more positive attitudes towards learning English through games. Regarding these results, it can be recommended that using games in teaching English is beneficial to beginners especially those in primary school. However, to do so, teachers ought to consider thoughtfully when selecting suitable games to be used. This is because it was found in the study that students with different learning styles and English ability performed differently when different types of games were used.

In particular, students knowledge based of this level requires that students have to be able to exchange and present information in English and are able to integrate speaking, listening and reading skills in order to communicate in particular topics such as, personal information, environment and hobbies. However, to be able to adopt a communicative approach into classes, teachers

need to know and to familiarize with it; otherwise, they continue traditionally teaching style.

1. Teacher writes the word “classroom” on the poster and asks students to write all the words they can think of that are connected to the words.

2. Speaking. Students change the underlined letters to make a new word.

BOOK -----LOOK

BOX-----FOX

PEN-----TEN

NINE-----FINE

BLOCK-----CLOCK

WALL-----TALL

CHAIR-----FAIR

3. Students guess and say what it is.

a) ---- a thing, where we keep books.

b) ---- a thing we usually have on the wall to write on in the classroom.

c) ---- a thing where pupils sit in class.

d) --- a place we study in.

4. Students find five classroom things and make up sentences with them.

Black ble

Pic case

Ch board

Book air

Ta ture

W all

For example: blackboard, picture, bookcase, wall...

a) There are many English books in bookcase.

b) My favourite picture is on the wall.

5. Word study. Find 13 words → ↓

U P E N D E S K Y

R E C L A S S B U

U N O T E B O O K

B C H A I R I C O

B I K B A G M H T

E L D L S C W A H

R U L E R R O E X

U T B C L O C K Z

6. Speaking. Chain drill. To practice using the new vocabulary.

Students turn each other by asking "What do you see in the classroom".

P1 I see a blackboard

P2 I see a table

P3

8. Students write their time-table and answer the questions:

№	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						

Questions:

- a) When do you have English?
- b) What lessons do you have on Tuesday?
- c) Have you got Uzbek on Saturday?
- d) How many times do you have Sport in a week?

9. Playing a game. Students guess what subject is it by answering yes\ no questions:

One of the students thinks a subject. The other students have to ask and guess what is it?

S_1 - Can we run and jump in it? – No, we can't

S_2 - Do we learn a foreign language? – No, we don't

S_3 - Can we use numbers in it? – Yes we can

S_3 - Is it math? – yes, it is.

Students write about their favourite subjects:

My favourite subjects are _____ and _____.

I like _____ because _____.

I have it on _____ and _____.

I like _____ because _____.

I have it on _____.

9. Students write connected words with weather in the poster and answer the questions:

Speaking. Answering the questions

- a) what's the weather like in spring?
- b) In which season is the weather hot?
- c) what weather do you like?
- d) Is it often cold in winter?
- e) Do you like winter and why?

10. Playing game "Snowball" (to throw a ball to each of pupils in turn saying a word belongs to weather. The pupil who catches a ball must make up sentence).

Example: S_1 cold

S_2 it is cold in winter

Writing. Students make up sentences:

is	often	cold	spring
	always	warm	autumn
		hot	March

It isn't usually fine April
sometimes dry September
October

Example: It isn't always hot in spring.

11. Playing a game "Domestic animals" (to throw a ball to each of pupils in turn. When they catch it, he/she must name a kind of animal.) The student who makes a mistake goes out of the game.

Teacher:

Student:

- | | |
|-------------------------------|-------------------|
| - Does it live in the forest? | - No, it doesn't. |
| - Does it live with people? | - Yes, it does. |
| - Does it drink milk? | - No, it doesn't. |
| - Does it eat grass? | - Yes, it does. |
| - Does it give milk? | - Yes, it does. |
| - Is it a goat? | - Yes, it is. |

12. Speaking: Food and meals:

1. In the south of China they eat rice, but in the north they eat noodles.

2. In Scandinavia, they eat a lot of herrings and the Portuguese love sardines.

3. Do you know that people in Europe don't eat so much fish; they eat more meat and sausages. In Germany and Poland there are 100 of different kinds of sausages.

4. In China (there is only one course), all the food is together on the table, and they eat with chopsticks.

5. In parts of India and the Middle East people use their fingers and bread to pick up the food.

Students work in groups and discuss these questions about their country.

- a) What is a typical breakfast?
- b) What does your family have for breakfast?
- c) Is lunch or dinner the main meal of the day?
- d) What is typical main meal?

13. Students work in groups. If team A writes Uzbek meals, team B will write English meals.

14. Students are divided into two groups. Uzbek students choose the name “Navruz” and English students choose the name – “Halloween”

Members of both group write the names of holidays on the board.

Uzbek national holidays:

Navruz, Rememberance Day, Ramazan and KurbanHayit, Independence Day...

English holidays:

Halloween, Christmas, New Year, Easter, Valentine’s Day...

15. Two Truths and a Lie: Students tell two truths and a lie about themselves and the other students must guess which one is the lie. Questions may be asked to discover the lie.

16. Stand in Order: The students must line up in a particular order using personal information about themselves, but without speaking.

Ex: Line up alphabetically using the first letter of your middle name

Line up according birthday month starting in January

17. The Candy Game: Teacher passes around a bowl of small candies, i.e. M&M's. Have everyone take as many as they want. They must then say one thing about themselves for every piece of candy they have.

18. Putting the Pieces Together: Teacher cuts one large square (about 8 in. x 8 in.) out of colored cardboard for each student and cuts each square into 8 smaller pieces of various shapes (rectangles, triangles, pentagons, etc.) Each square should be unique. Teacher divides the class into groups of 5 and gives each group the scrambled pieces for 5 of the squares. Each member of the group must be given 8 pieces. Their job is to put the squares together again without talking. Students cannot ask for someone else's piece. They can only take another student's piece without asking and give that student one of theirs. Students continue giving and taking pieces until everyone in the group has made a square. This should take about 5-10 minutes. When they finish they can talk about what they just did. And they will have a lot to say! If the activity is successful and moving along quickly enough. Teacher can repeat the activity.

19. Ball Toss/Group Juggle: Good for a group of at least 12 and up to 30 where some people know each other, but the whole group is still getting acquainted: (Have 3 tennis balls handy. Get the group in a circle. Facilitator tosses 1 ball to someone in the group whose name they know saying their name and then the other person's name (e.g. Sandy to John). John (person who receives the ball) tosses ball to someone whose name he knows (e.g. John to Phil). Phil tosses to someone whose name he knows and so on, saying both names all the way around the circle. The ball is tossed to each person one time only until everyone in the circle gets it and all names have been said. Then the facilitator starts again and tosses the balls to the same person (Sandy to John to Phil, etc.) only this time with 2 balls in succession (not at the same time) saying both names, both times. Balls get tossed to the same people they were originally tossed to; first one ball, then the next, all the way around the circle stopping when they get back to the facilitator. Then the facilitator starts again only with all three balls this time. Saying names each time, all three balls get tossed, in succession, in the same order until they get back to the facilitator. By the time there are three balls going, it gets pretty chaotic and fun. By now all names have been said so many times everyone should have a pretty good idea of who's who and they are pretty warmed up and ready to go. If (I should say, when) someone drops a ball, simply give them a

chance to chase it down and just pick up where you left off-no need to start again.
(CAN ALSO BE USED AS AN ENERGIZER)

In conclusion, using games is an efficient way to teach English in the classroom. This way you get the best results in the classroom. It arises students' motivation. Games prepare young learners for life and they acquire positive social attitudes.